

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' SKILLS TO SOLVE LOGICAL PROBLEMS FROM PHYSICS

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Abstract. *This article shows the importance of using logical problems in physics lessons, taking into account the fact that logical problems are rarely used in the development of students' scientific worldviews, quick thinking, mental and intellectual abilities.*

Keywords: *logic, logical theory, method of thinking, table method, graph method, logical problems.*

In higher educational institutions, the role of problem solving in forming the scientific worldview of physics students, understanding the essence of physical phenomena and laws through in-depth observation, increasing student activity and forming interest in science, and performing calculation work is of particular importance. It is known that in the following years four (quantitative, qualitative, experimental and graphic) methods of solving problems in physics will be used. Each of these methods contributes to the deeper assimilation of the content of theoretical materials by students, remembers and applies physical formulas in the process of solving problems, makes students interested in science by solving interesting problems in classes, confirms the validity of theoretical information by conducting experiments, and develops graphic imaginations. However, there is also a type of issues that are rarely used in the educational process in recent years. However, these problems teach students to think quickly, to connect physical laws with each other, to take into account the interaction, to train the mind, to make the right decision in difficult situations. These are logical issues.

Logical problems in physics teach students about natural phenomena; revealing the content of knowledge of mechanics, molecular physics, electromagnetism, optics, atomic and nuclear physics, correct (true) thinking in learning physical concepts through induction and deduction methods, knowing the truth, including the relationship between thoughts teaches to observe and discuss about the rules.

Below are some examples of logical problems that can be used in physics classes.

Issue 1. Measurable quantities. What has no length, depth, width, height, but can be measured?

Answer. Time and temperature can be measured without length, depth, width, or height.

Issue 2. Why do the trunks of trees whiten in early spring?

Answer. So that the trunk of trees does not wake up quickly in early spring.

Issue 3. Determination of the diameter of a thin wire. How to measure the diameter of a thin wire with maximum accuracy using only a ruler and a pencil?

Answer: wrap the wire tightly around the pencil (round, without edge) and make at least ten turns (the more accurate the measurement is, the better the result will be). Then measure in millimeters from the first circle to the last circle with a ruler and divide by the number of circles formed.

Logical tasks are the most effective tool for developing logic and thinking in students, perhaps even adults. Solving a logic problem involves a complex thought process. This allows for the execution of certain logical sequence of actions, working with concepts, use of various logical constructions, construction of a clear and correct chain of thinking with intermediate and final conclusions. Unlike many mathematical and other types of problems, the main thing in solving logical problems is not to find the quantitative properties of an object, but to identify and analyze the relationships between all the objects of the problem.

A specific strategy for solving a logical problem can be summarized in the following five steps:

1. Paying attention to the essence of the matter and understanding.
2. Description of interrelationships and relationships between physical laws that make up the essence of the matter.
3. Planning a solution.
4. Execution of the plan.
5. Interpretation and evaluation of the solution

The knowledge and thought processes used at each stage depend on students' discipline. Taking into account the specifics of physics, we choose to define and interpret the five steps of a general strategy for solving logical problems as follows:

1. Paying attention to the essence of the matter and understanding. At this stage, it is necessary to develop a logical description of the problem, first, with the help of a sketch, visualize the phenomena described in the problem, write a simple statement of what you want to know, recall the physics ideas that may be useful in the problem, and describe the approach you will use.

2. Description of interrelationships and relationships between physical laws that make up the essence of the matter. At this stage, in order to prepare for a logical solution, it is necessary to understand the problem correctly, first, to find the essence of the problem by simplifying it by describing it with a diagram in terms of physical interactions, natural phenomena and necessary concepts, quantities, by naming certain mathematical parameters, recalling the quantities, using the physical ideas collected in step 1, it is necessary to write an expression that shows how these physical quantities are related according to physical or mathematical principles.

3. Plan a solution: In this step, you turn your reasoning description into a set of expressions that mathematically describe the problem, using the ideas and propositions gathered in step 2, and write a plan to see how they lead to a solution.

4. Execution of the plan: In this stage of planning, combining the previous ideas and proposals in a planned manner to determine the most suitable, then connecting all the known quantities with each other, calculating the numerical value of the desired unknown (target) quantity need to be determined.

5. Interpretation and evaluation of the solution: Finally, it is necessary to check whether the given question is answered correctly and rationally, and evaluate the result.

In conclusion, we can pay attention to the following suggestions when solving problems in physics:

Thus, qualitative, quantitative, experimental and graphical problems are the same in physics classes using logic problems in a row:

- first of all, students need to make a chain of thoughts correctly to find a solution to the problem, to think quickly and intellectually, to make a judgment or a conclusion;

- secondly, by using a logical problem in teacher's lectures attracts students' attention, encourages intellectual thinking, makes lessons interesting and attractive;
 - thirdly, students will try to find a solution to the problem in future lessons, there is a process of mutual exchange of ideas between students, students pay attention to the lessons, a student listens and waits for the next logical question from the teacher, that is, in turn, increases the efficiency of physics classes and the intellectual development of students serves to form abilities.
 - fourthly, innovative ideas and visions of science and technology are born in students with recent achievements
1. The effectiveness of teaching to solve logical problems from physics is determined through their comparative analysis.
 2. In lecture classes - in the process of imparting new knowledge, when students are tired of formulas, logical problems are given in order to activate the students, and until the skill is acquired, the teacher makes the students think together on a group scale.
 3. Logical problems for individual and group solving are offered as homework.
 4. At first, simpler, algorithmic problems are offered, otherwise the students will not believe in their own strength and even become bored with this subject.
 5. It is recommended to use logical problems in the process of written work and intermediate controls.

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